

Studies on the Molecular Complexes of Para-benzoquinone and Amino Acids. Part I

A. K. CHATTOPADHYAY and S. C. LAHIRI

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, West Bengal, India

Manuscript received 8 September 1978, revised 29 August 1979, accepted 9 April 1980

Para-benzoquinone has been found to form pinkish-red complexes with amino acids having absorption maxima lying between 480 nm to 510 nm. The complex formation is facilitated by warming and the complexes are appreciably stable. The stoichiometry of the complexes formed between PBQ with most amino acids have been found to be 1 : 2 by Job's method of continuous variation. The stability constants of the complexes in solution have also been calculated.

QUINONES are well known for their bacteriostatic, antifungal, antitumor activities as well as their blood clotting properties¹. These properties make them a potential field of further study. However, physico-chemical properties of relatively few biologically active quinones have been made. The high chemical reactivity and ability to form charge-transfer complexes²⁻⁴ gave us impetus to study the possible charge-transfer properties of quinones with amino acids, substances of vital interest of all living matters. The present communication deals with the results of our investigations on the complex formation of amino acids with para-benzoquinone.

Experimental

Amino acids (glycine, DL- α -alanine, glutamine, γ -amino-butyric acids, valine, proline, arginine, methionine, histidine and tyrosine, except G.R.—E. Merck variety) were purified by repeated crystallization from alcohol-water and drying. *p*-Benzoquinone or PBQ (Hopkins-Williams) was purified by steam distillation which gave bright yellow crystals. The purity of the sample was checked by melting point determination.

Solutions were prepared by direct weighing. Since PBQ is only slightly soluble in water, it was dissolved in little alcohol. The aforesaid amino acids absorb in the U.V. region. PBQ absorbs strongly in U.V. region as well as in visible region. Amino acids when added to PBQ show marked change in O.D. values and generally give pinkish-red complexes with absorption maxima lying between 480 nm to 510 nm depending on the nature of the amino acids. The wave lengths of maximum absorption of different complexes are given in Table I. The colour of the complexes becomes maximum in about 40 to 50 hours depending on the nature of the amino acids. The excess addition of amino acids depends the colour of the complexes. It is noteworthy to mention that the colour formation is facilitated on warming the solution; no decolorization takes place on cooling

which ensures the appreciable stability of the complexes. The complexes have been found to be temperature reversible. O.D. values increase on heating but decrease on cooling similar to the observations of Slifkin *et al*⁵ in case of proline-chloranil complexes.

The composition of the complexes were determined by Job's method of continuous variation. Equimolar solutions were prepared by mixing PBQ and amino acids of the same strength in the ratio (1 : 11, 2 : 10 ; 10 : 2, 11 : 1) and left for equilibrium for sufficient time (usually more than 40 hours) and O.D. readings were noted at the wavelength of maximum absorption. The O.D. values of the corresponding blank solutions (having the same composition as in the original solution except the amino acids) were also measured. The stoichiometry of amino acids and PBQ complex were found in the ratio 2 : 1 in almost all cases except for Arginine-PBQ (1 : 1), Tyrosine-PBQ (1 : 1) and Histidine-PBQ (1 : 2). The stoichiometry has also been supported by the conductometric measurement. The conductance values increased and became maximum when PBQ and amino acids were in the ratios noted earlier.

It is likely that 1 : 1 complexes may also be formed. However, our attempts to identify the (1 : 1) compounds by adding amino acids to the large excess of quinone proved futile.

It had been found that O.D. values increased with increase in amino acid concentrations and became constant when concentrations of amino acids were high (about 40 fold excess). The property was utilized to determine the extinction coefficients of the complexes. The O.D. values of the solutions containing 40 fold excess or more of amino acids to different concentrations of quinone were measured at the wavelength of maximum absorption. Under these conditions, the concentrations of the

complexes could be taken equal to the concentrations of quinone [except in the case of PBQ and Histidine complex (2:1) where the concentrations of the complex is equal to half of the concentration of quinone]. The extinction coefficients are given in Table 1.

Colorimetric Estimation of Quinone :

Though quinone absorbs in the visible region but the extinction coefficient is too small ($\epsilon_{425nm} = 25.12^6$ whereas our values are $\epsilon_{450nm} = 28$ and $\epsilon_{500nm} = 15$) to utilise it for the quantitative estimation of quinone. The fact that the quinone is quantitatively converted into the molecular complexes by the addition of large excess of amino acids may be used for the colorimetric estimation of quinone. The quinone (in little alcohol) should be treated with excess of amino acids (about 50 times or more), kept at 50° in a waterbath for about 1-2 hours and the resultant solution should be quantitatively transferred to a volumetric flask and made upto the mark. From the O.D. readings of the solution and the corresponding blank at 500 nm and the extinction coefficients, determined previously, concentrations of quinone (10^{-3} to $10^{-4}M$) may be estimated. With arginine, the extinction coefficient is sufficiently high at $\lambda = 555$ nm, absorption of quinone is negligibly small to be neglected and the blank determinations could also be avoided.

Determination of the Stability Constant of the Complexes :

For the determination of the stability constant of the complexes, different concentrations of PBQ [concentration range 10^{-4} — $10^{-3}(M)$] and amino acids [concentration range 10^{-4} — $10^{-3}(M)$] were mixed and kept for about 50 hours at 25°. O.D. readings of the solutions as well as the corresponding blanks were taken. The concentrations of complex were taken, The concentration of complexes were calculated from extinction coefficients and O.D. values.

All optical density measurements were taken with a Beckman DU 2 spectrophotometer kept at 25°. The

conductance measurements were done with the aid of a Leeds-Northrup Model 4959 conductance bridge with a sensitivity of $\pm 0.1\%$.

Calculation of Stability of the Complexes :

The stability constants of the complexes

can be written as $K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2}$

where x = concentration of the complex formed, a and b are the initial concentrations of quinone and amino acids respectively.

Now $d_1 = \epsilon_1 a l$

and $d_2 = \epsilon_1 (a-x) l + \epsilon_2 x l$

$d_2 - d_1 = (\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) x l$

$x = \frac{d_2 - d_1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)} \dots (1)$

(Since $l = 1$ cm)

where ϵ_1 = extinction coefficient of quinone
 ϵ_2 = extinction coefficient of complex

The results are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussions

A large number of complexes have been reported for the interactions of quinone with amino acids^{7,8}. Sur⁹ studied the donor-acceptor complexes of *p*-benzoquinone with amino acids (glycine, alanine, aspartic acid and glutamine) and inferred from the stability constant measurements (assuming 1:1 complex) that the strength of the donors is in the order glycine > glutamine > alanine > aspartic acid.

However, the colour development is not instantaneous and the complete complex formation requires

TABLE—1

Complexes	λ_{max}	ϵ_2	ϵ_1	K
1. PBQ : Glycine	495 nm	270	16.5	$9.4(\pm 0.3) \times 10^4$
2. PBQ : DL- α -Alanine	485 nm	400	19	$6.5(\pm 0.2) \times 10^4$
3. PBQ : γ -Amino Butyric acid	-	302.5 ($\lambda = 490$ nm)	18	$1.7(\pm 0.1) \times 10^4$
4. PBQ : Methionine	495 nm	504	16.8	$2.3(\pm 0.1) \times 10^5$
5. PBQ : L-Glutamine	490 nm	453	18	$7.6(\pm 0.4) \times 10^5$
6. PBQ : Tyrosine	-	305 ($\lambda = 490$ nm)	18	$1.9(\pm 0.3) \times 10^4$
7. PBQ : Histidine	-	1800 ($\lambda = 500$ nm)	15	$5.1(\pm 0.3) \times 10^5$
8. PBQ : Valin	497 nm	480	16	$3.8(\pm 0.2) \times 10^4$
9. PBQ : Proline	515 nm	930	10	$1.2(\pm 0.1) \times 10^5$
10. PBQ : Arginine	555 nm	1431.5	-	$6.2(\pm 0.2) \times 10^2$

The equilibrium constant had also been verified from measurements at different wavelengths.

appreciably long time indicating molecular complex formation or chemical reaction rather than charge transfer complex contrary to the observation by Sur.

Slifkin and co-workers^{7,10,11} studied the C.T. complexes of amino acids with chloranil in aqueous ethanol with peaks at Ca 295 nm. A slowly developing pH-dependent new peak appeared (9 hr at pH 9, 24 hr at pH 7 and 3 days at pH 4) at longer wavelengths between Ca 350 nm and 390 nm.

The rate of growth of the peak have been ascribed to the rate scheme

The pH-dependence and the slow rate of the formation of complexes have been explained on the basis of conversion of Zwitter ion form (Z) to Neutral form (N) according to the equilibria $Z \rightleftharpoons N$ as the reaction proceeds and the pH increases.

The new peaks whose position change with pH have been ascribed to intrinsic band of chloranil shifted on complexing to that of the negative ion at 426 nm due to contribution of ionic structures to the structure of the complexed ion¹¹.

But it is not clear 1) Why the peak of the complexes should change so much ?

2) Why K_{form} should change with pH and wavelength ?

3) Why no account has been taken to the change in chloranil concentration due to its conversion to ionic form in calculating K and ϵ from Benesi—Hildebrand equation ?

Our studies reveal some important aspects. These are :

- 1) The marked increase in colour indicating the retention of quinonoid structure.
- 2) The relatively rapid effervescence of CO_2 when Na_2CO_3 was added to the solutions of the complexes than when added to amino acids alone.
- 3) The increase in conductivity of the solution of complexes is due to the presence of two carboxyl groups. Amino acids being 'Zwitter ions' are less conducting.
- 4) The compounds formed are highly soluble in water.

These facts lead us to suggest the following reaction schemes similar to that reported by Foster⁸, Woker

and Antener¹², Loffe and Khavin¹³, Michalek and Szarkowska¹⁴. This type of additions to quinone is quite familiar particularly in case of thiol compounds which is supposed to occur in a number of biochemical processes i.e., in the antibacterial activity of quinone^{15,16}.

or
b)

This may proceed via intermediate hydroquinone formation.

The fact that the compounds formed are highly soluble in water (more than amino acids) and less soluble in alcohol or other organic solvents leads us to believe that except for proline complexes of quinone, other compounds are of the type (Y). But we are not absolutely sure regarding the structures.

Absorption maxima are almost the same in all the cases indicating that almost all the compounds are of similar type. The stability constants of these compounds are also of the same order of magnitude as expected. The value of the stability constant decreases with branching but increases slightly with increasing chain length.

The 1 : 1 compound formation of tyrosine may be due to the involvement of OH-group as well as NH_2 group of the amino acid. The steric factor may be responsible for 1 : 1 compound formation in arginine. This amino acid is strongly basic due to its guanidino group and the stability, therefore, decreases as the amino acids are known to be good electron donors in acidic solution—a fact which is responsible for the change in K values in chloranil amino acid complexes¹⁰. The large bathochromic shift in arginine amino acid compound indicates greater conjugation.

One of the notable features is that the reactions are exergonic in character ($\Delta G = -6$ to -7 K. cal/mole in most cases) and can therefore, be utilised by suitable coupling mechanism to drive endergonic processes for analogizing complex biochemical substances.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., Government of India, for a Research Fellowship.

References

1. B. PULLMAN and A. PULLMAN, *Quantum Biochemistry*, Interscience Publishers, Chapter XI, 1963.
2. A. SZENT-GYORGYI, *Introduction to a Submolecular Biology*, Academic Press, 1960.
3. L. J. ANDREWS and R. M. KEIFER, 'Molecular Complexes in Organic Chem.', Holden-Day, Sanfrancisco, Calif, 1964.
4. R. FOSTER, *Organic Charge-transfer Complexes*, Academic Press, London, 1970.
5. M. A. SLIFKIN and J. G. HEATHCOTE, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1967, 23A, 2893.
6. J. W. DIDMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2363.
7. M. A. SLIFKIN, *Charge-transfer Interactions of Biomolecules*, Academic Press. London and New York, 1971.
8. R. FOSTER in *Molecular complexes Vol. 2*, Ed. R. FOSTER, Elek Science, London 1974, Chapter-5.
9. S. SUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 379.
10. J. B. BIRKS and M. A. SLIFKIN, *Nature*, 1963, 197, 42.
11. M. A. SLIFKIN, *Nature*, 1963, 198, 1301.
12. G. WOKER and I. ANTENER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1937, 20, 1260.
13. I. S. LOFFE and Z. Y. KHAVIN, *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, 49, 6169.
14. H. MICHALEK and L. SZARKOWSKA, *Acta Biochim. Polon.*, 1959, 6, 399.
15. J. M. SNELL and A. WEISSBERGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 450.
16. M. SCHUBERT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 712.